

SOME ASPECTS OF IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SERVICE TO POULTRY FARMS

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Abstract. In the article, some aspects observed in improving the efficiency of services to poultry farms, the circumstances that make it necessary, and directions for the development of services in the future are suggested.

Keywords. service, efficiency, poultry, profitability, productivity, climate change, competitiveness.

On the basis of the agrarian reforms implemented in our country, emphasis is being placed on ensuring food security, employment of the population, and the formation of an additional source of income, as well as increasing the opportunities for creating added value by diversifying production. For these tasks, one of the urgent directions is to develop each link of the economic sectors separately, to ensure their mutual integration, and to create a basis for their sustainable growth in terms of volume and quality.

If we pay attention to the dynamics of long-term development of agriculture, it can be observed that the links of management, management and service to them, which are part of the network, are developing steadily. If we look at the cross-section of networks, inclusive links of state management, forms of economic management based on market principles and individual directions of scientific and technical services have been formed and are developing in separate areas of agriculture and animal husbandry. All this has a positive effect on the sustainable development of the agricultural industry in our country and ensuring its competitiveness.

However, the development of the economy, globalization, acceleration of information flow, scientific and technical progress, digitalization, and the increasing sensitivity of industries to the effects of external factors related to various political crises require the improvement of scientific research in their specific areas.

In this regard, animal husbandry, which is one of the integral parts of the agrarian network, is subject to various fluctuations due to the effects of the mentioned factors as well as adaptation to climate changes. In particular, directions for the production of products that have a significant share in the

consumption basket of the population of our country, such as cattle breeding, poultry farming, and fishing, are clearly noticeable.

According to industry experts, there are 3 important conditions for sustainable development of animal husbandry, which are closely related to breeding, quality feed supply and infrastructure. The only direction that maintains these 3 conditional development factors as a whole is directly related to the service, and each of the 3 factors is characterized by the service quality of the network. In other words, breeding includes a set of scientific supplies, science-based services, and nutrition includes the services related to proper nutrition based on this ration and the cultivation of this nutritious food. At the same time, the quality of services and their condition are formed and developed directly depending on the condition of the existing infrastructure.

Therefore, improving the quality of services at all stages of animal husbandry, expanding the scope of scientific research related to it, and relying on science in the development of the industry are considered to be one of the current trends today.

This is particularly evident in poultry farming, where a significant part of the poultry and poultry products grown is contributed by small and scattered farms, and at the same time industrial poultry is developing steadily, providing them with nutritious food, fighting against diseases, actual directions to be implemented in the development of purebred poultry and tasks awaiting scientific solution is preserved.

Economists such as U.Kuchchiev, U.Sadullaev, A.Abruev, M.Yakhyaev, O'.Egamberdiev [1-5], who conduct research on the development of the livestock industry in our country, and M.Rakhmataliev, who directly conducted research on the development of the poultry industry, Agrarian economists such as O. Albekov, I. Achilov [4-6] also improve the quality of services in poultry farming, especially they emphasize the need to increase the scale of financial and digital services together with basic services such as veterinary medicine.

Based on the above, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of services in the poultry industry in our country, and based on its importance, researches aimed at increasing the quality and scope of services in the following directions become urgent. In particular:

- Scientific services related to the analysis of nutrients in the context of the increase of GMO and other genetically modified products and the increased demand for organic products in developed countries;

- digital livestock services aimed at regular monitoring of poultry development, nutrition, productivity and diseases, humidity and temperature monitoring;

- consulting services aimed at formation and development of experience and skills;

- breeding services aimed at increasing the productivity of poultry and related scientific and technical development services;

- waste processing, disposal, climate services aimed at ensuring green energy efficiency, etc.

In general, the poultry industry is developing in a unique way in our country, and the issue of increasing the efficiency of services in the sector should be aimed at solving the complexity of providing services to farmers who lack the financial potential for investment and industrialized poultry enterprises with potential. At the same time, it is required that the services provided in this network should not lag behind global science and include the optimal implementation of digital technologies. Otherwise, the poultry industry of our country will reduce its competitiveness and create new gaps in the consumer market.

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